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Motivation

- Large-format additive manufacturing (LFAM) requires precise **control of bead geometry** to ensure part accuracy and mechanical performance.
- Synchronizing screw-driven extrusion flow with gantry motion is critical to **avoid over and under extrusion**.
- Thermal history during printing plays a key role in **interlayer bonding** through reheating and polymer diffusion mechanics.
- Infrared thermography enables real-time monitoring of surface temperature evolution, **cooling and reheating** behavior.

Experimental Workflow for Bead Synchronization and Thermal Imaging

Pellet-fed LFAM Printing

- Carbon fiber reinforced polycarbonate (PC-CF)
- Nozzle diameter : 0.3in Ø
- Barrel & Nozzle Temperature 310°C
- RPM range tested: 130-370 RPM

Bead Size Calibration

- 20 seconds extrusion trials at fixed RPM
- Material collected and weighed to determine melt flow rate
- Flow rate used to tune slicer deposition speed

Melt Flow Rate (MFR)

$$\text{Bead height} \times \text{Bead width} \times \text{Deposition speed}$$

Thermal History Acquisition

- 40-layer vertical wall (2 beads wide)
- FLIR T62101 IR camera fixed on bed, front-facing view
- Dwell times controlled to achieve desired later time

Bead Size Synchronization

Calibrated output = Consistent beads

No voids

Enables consistent bead geometry

Fracture mechanics

Additional work

DIC

SEM

Thermal History

60 second layer time → 230 RPM, 1.69 in/sec

Increase in thermal mass

Below T_g

Above T_g

Optimal interlayer bonding

Conclusion and Insights

- The findings show a direct linear relationship between screw RPM and volumetric output, enabling bead size control.
- Consistent bead dimensions are critical for layer quality and mechanical repeatability in LFAM.
- IR thermography effectively captured layer-specific thermal histories.
- Higher layers experience extended high-temperature exposure due to thermal mass, potentially enhancing interlayer bonding.
- This methodology provides a framework for experimentally tuning process parameters to optimize part quality.

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